

1 **Study of the Liquid / Vapor Interfacial Properties of**
2 **Concentrated Polyelectrolyte – Surfactant Mixtures Using**
3 **Surface Tensiometry and Neutron Reflectometry: Equilibrium,**
4 **Adsorption Kinetics and Dilational Rheology**

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1 Abstract

2 The adsorption of mixtures of poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC) and
3 sodium N-lauroyl-N-methyltaurate (SLMT) at the water / vapor interface has been studied
4 using drop profile tensiometry and neutron reflectometry. This study sheds light on the
5 mechanisms involved in the adsorption of polyelectrolyte – oppositely charged surfactants by
6 the characterization of both equilibrium and dynamics features associated with the layer
7 formation at the fluid interface. The results are discussed in terms of an adsorption –
8 equilibration of the interfacial layers as a two-step process: the initial stages involve the
9 adsorption of polyelectrolyte – surfactant complexes formed in the bulk, and a subsequent
10 stage involves reorganization of the interface. This work contributes to the understanding of
11 the physico-chemical features of systems that undergo complex bulk and interfacial
12 interactions with importance in science and technology.

13

1 **1. Introduction**

2 The study of polymer – surfactant mixtures has undergone spectacular growth in recent years,
3 mainly due to their interest in different technological and industrial fields, from drug delivery
4 systems to mineral processing, and from tertiary oil recovery to cosmetic formulations for
5 shampoos and hair care products.¹⁻⁸ Among the different existing mixtures that include
6 polymers and surfactants, those containing oppositely charged components present big
7 importance due to their recognized interest in many technological fields.^{2, 4} However, there
8 are many issues related to the physico-chemical behavior of such mixtures that remain
9 unclear, especially when their interactions with fluid interfaces are considered.^{3, 9-12} The study
10 of polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures at the water / vapor interface has been carried out
11 mainly on the basis of surface tension measurements.¹³⁻¹⁶ However, in recent years the
12 development of neutron reflectometry has provided access to information related to the
13 structure and composition of such interfaces.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Despite the extensive studies on the
14 interfacial properties of the aforementioned systems, the scenario is rather complex, mainly
15 due to the fact that polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures are strongly affected by non-
16 equilibrium effects. Campbell and Varga have recently provided a detailed picture of the
17 interfacial behavior of polyelectrolyte – oppositely charged surfactant mixtures and its
18 correlations to the bulk phase behavior: depletion of the interface as a result of aggregation in
19 the bulk,²⁰ and enrichment of the interface as a result of direct interactions of the formed
20 aggregates.²¹ This physical picture was based on an understanding of bulk non-equilibrium
21 effects that had been investigated extensively over the last years.²²⁻²⁵

22 It is worth mentioning that most of the studies in the literature concern steady state interfacial
23 properties of layers formed by polymer – surfactant mixtures. Although the observed
24 behavior may be far from equilibrium, technological and industrial problems are dominated
25 by systems that rely on the response of the interface to mechanical perturbations, i.e. their

1 rheological response.²⁶⁻²⁸ The seminal works on the interfacial rheological characterization of
2 polyelectrolyte – charged surfactants were carried out by Regismond et al.,²⁹⁻³⁰ and showed
3 the existence of a synergetic effect of the polymer – surfactant interaction on the adsorption
4 at fluid interfaces of different mixtures. Later, Monteux et al.³¹ tried to correlate the
5 rheological response, both shear and dilational, to the stability of foams in mixtures of
6 poly(4-styrenesulfonate of sodium) and dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide at the water /
7 vapor interface, and found that the adsorption layers showed a behavior typical of interfacial
8 gels, inhibiting bubble coalescence and foam drainage. This physical picture was in
9 agreement with studies of Bhattacharyya et al.³² More recently, Noskov et al.³³⁻³⁶ have
10 studied the response upon dilation of several mixtures formed by polyelectrolytes and
11 surfactants bearing opposite charges. They concluded that in most cases the interfacial
12 response upon mechanical deformation depends on the heterogeneity of the formed layers. It
13 is important to recall that most of the aforementioned studies considered dilute mixtures,
14 which present a composition that is far from consumer products. Consumer products contain
15 polyelectrolyte concentrations well above the overlapping concentration c^* ³⁷⁻³⁸, i.e. the
16 polymer concentration above which the physico-chemical properties of the polyelectrolyte
17 lose their dependence on the molecular weight, assuming for PDADMAC a value about 0.4
18 g/L,³⁹ and it is known that the properties of diluted and concentrated polymer systems are
19 different.⁴⁰ This situation was also found to be the case in our previous works.⁴¹⁻⁴² Thus, it is
20 expected that the dynamics of interfaces may be also affected by the nature of the solutions.

21 The present work is devoted on the study of the interfacial properties, both equilibrium and
22 dynamics, of layers formed by poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC) and
23 sodium N-lauroyl-N-methyltaurate (SLMT). The interest in studies of this polyelectrolyte –
24 surfactant mixture is associated with their potential industrial interest for their application in
25 cosmetics. SLMT presents similar performance for cleansing and conditioning purposes to

1 sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), which has been for long time the preferred surfactant used in
2 the fabrication of shampoos and hair care products, but SLMT is more friendly for human
3 and environmental health.^{41, 43} Furthermore, SLMT is less susceptible to degradation than
4 SDS.⁴⁴

5 The adsorption kinetics at the water / vapor interface has been measured in terms of the
6 dynamic surface tension using a drop profile tensiometer and the dynamic surface excess by
7 neutron reflectometry. Furthermore, the response against mechanical perturbations has been
8 studied using a drop profile tensiometer. Even though it would be desirable to correlate the
9 complex experimental findings with the physical phenomena present in this type of mixtures,
10 there is no theory available for mixtures of a polymer and a surfactant yet. It is expected that
11 this work may help to shed light on the complex physico-chemical behavior of these systems.

12

13 **2. Experimental Section**

14 **2.1 Chemicals.** Ultrapure deionized water used for cleaning and solution preparation had a
15 resistivity higher than 18 M Ω ·cm and a total organic content lower than 6 ppm (Younglin 370
16 Series, South Korea). PDADMAC was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany), and had
17 an average molecular weight in the 100 – 200 kDa range, and was used without further
18 purification. SLMT and perdeuterated SLMT were synthesized and purified following the
19 procedures described in Ref. ⁴². For neutron reflectometry experiments, deuterated water
20 (D₂O, isotopic purity > 99.9 wt%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany).

21 The pH of all solutions was adjusted to 5.6 using glacial acetic acid (purity > 99 %) and the
22 ionic strength was kept constant by adding 0.3 wt% of KCl (purity > 99.9 %). The
23 PDADMAC concentration was kept constant at 0.5 wt% in all the samples.

1 The PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures were prepared by weight following the procedure
2 described in our previous work.⁴²

3 **2.2 Techniques**

4 *a. Surface tension measurements.* The dynamic and equilibrium surface tensions (γ) of SLMT
5 solutions and PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures were measured using a Profile Analysis
6 Tensiometer (PAT1-Sinterface, Germany).⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ This method relies on the acquisition of the
7 profile of a solution drop formed at the tip of a steel capillary. The γ value is obtained by
8 fitting the acquired profile of the axis-symmetric drop using the Laplace equation. The
9 adsorption at the water / vapor interface was measured until steady state was reached. Special
10 care was taken to minimize evaporation effects as was detailed in our previous work.⁴²

11 The drop profile analysis tensiometer also allows obtaining information on the response of
12 the interface upon dilation, providing information on the frequency dependences of the
13 complex viscoelastic modulus in the 5 – 200 mHz range. All experiments were carried out at
14 $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The surface pressure is defined as $\Pi(c) = \gamma_0 - \gamma(c)$, where γ_0 is the surface
15 tension of the bare water / vapor interface and $\gamma(c)$ is the surface tension of the solution/vapor
16 interface.

17 *b. Neutron reflectometry.* Neutron reflectometry experiments were carried out using the time-
18 of-flight horizontal reflectometer FIGARO at the Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL, Grenoble,
19 France).⁴⁸ Neutron reflectivity profiles of $\log_{10} R(Q)$ were recorded with neutrons of
20 wavelengths $\lambda = 2 - 30 \text{ \AA}$ at an incident angle $\theta = 0.622^\circ$, where R is the reflectivity and

21 $Q = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin \theta$ is the momentum transfer. The analysis was carried out using Motofit.⁴⁹

22 Mixtures of PDADMAC with deuterated SLMT were measured in air contrast matched
23 water, which is a mixture of 8.1% v/v D₂O in H₂O that has zero scattering length density.¹⁷ A

1 direct measure of the surfactant surface excess in the mixture was performed by neglecting
 2 the minimal scattering contribution of the polyelectrolyte. Additional details of the
 3 experimental procedure and calculations used can be found in Ref. ⁴².

4

5 **3. Theory**

6 Thermodynamics models for describing the adsorption of surface active species at the water /
 7 vapor interface can help to the better understanding of the physico – chemical bases
 8 underlying the adsorption process. For simple surfactants, the Frumkin model is one of the
 9 most extended models. It reads as follows⁵⁰

$$10 \quad bc = \frac{\Gamma \omega}{1 - \Gamma \omega} e^{-2a\Gamma \omega} \quad (1)$$

$$11 \quad -\frac{\Pi \omega}{RT} = \ln(1 - \Gamma \omega) + a(\Gamma \omega)^2 \quad (2)$$

12 where c and Γ are the bulk concentration and the surface excess, respectively, ω represents
 13 the area per molecule at the saturated interface, b corresponds to the adsorption equilibrium
 14 constant, a is the parameter of molecular interaction, and R and T are the gas constant and the
 15 absolute temperature, respectively.

16 The theoretical description of the experimental results for polymer – surfactant mixtures on
 17 the basis of traditional thermodynamics models is difficult, mainly due to the particular
 18 characteristic of such systems as will be discussed below. Therefore, only an empirical
 19 description of the experimental findings reminiscent of a theoretical model describing the
 20 adsorption of molecules in two different states at the interface can be used to give a
 21 qualitative analysis of the complex phenomenology associated with the adsorption of

1 polymer – surfactant mixtures at the water / vapor interface.⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹ The set of empirical
 2 equations are summarized as follows,

$$3 \quad bc = \frac{\Gamma_1 \omega}{(1 - \Gamma \omega)^{\omega_1 / \omega}} \quad (3)$$

$$4 \quad -\frac{\Pi \omega}{RT} = \ln(1 - \Gamma \omega) \quad (4)$$

5 with Γ_i ($i = 1, 2$) and ω_i ($i = 1, 2$) being the surface excesses and the area per molecule for
 6 molecules in different states, and $b = b_I$ is the adsorption equilibrium constant in state 1. The
 7 total surface excess Γ and the mean area per molecule ω can be defined as

$$8 \quad \Gamma = \Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2 \quad (5)$$

$$9 \quad \omega \Gamma = \theta = \omega_1 \Gamma_1 + \omega_2 \Gamma_2 \quad (6)$$

10 where θ represents the surface coverage. The ratio of adsorbed molecules in the two different
 11 states is given by

$$12 \quad \frac{\Gamma_2}{\Gamma_1} = \exp\left(\frac{\omega_2 - \omega_1}{\omega}\right) \left(\frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1}\right)^\alpha \exp\left(-\frac{\Pi(\omega_2 - \omega_1)}{RT}\right) \quad (7)$$

13 where α is a constant accounting for the potential different adsorption of the species in the
 14 state 2 than in state 1. Furthermore, it is necessary to consider the role of the two-dimensional
 15 compressibility ε of the molecules in state 1,

$$16 \quad \omega_1 = \omega_{10} (1 - \varepsilon \Pi \theta) \quad (8)$$

17 where ω_{10} is the area per molecule in the state 1 at $\Pi = 0$. For the scope of this study, the
 18 empirical equations try to stress the complexity of the adsorption process of polymer –
 19 surfactant mixtures. Thus, the reported parameter must be considered only as a set of fitting

1 parameters providing predictions for the concentration dependences of the surface pressure
 2 Π , the surface excess Γ and the viscoelastic moduli ε^* . Such predictions can be compared
 3 with the experimental results obtained by tensiometry and neutron reflectometry.

4 Moreover, the adsorption models allow one to obtain a qualitative prediction on the
 5 adsorption kinetics at the interface as the the temporal dependences of the surface tension and
 6 of the surface excess for a specific concentration of surface active specie. For this purpose,
 7 the dependences of the surface excesses extracted from the analysis of the surface tension
 8 isotherms must be combined with the Ward-Tordai equation,⁵¹

$$9 \quad \Gamma(t) = 2\sqrt{\frac{D}{\pi}} \left[c_0\sqrt{t} - \int_0^{\sqrt{t}} c(0, t-t') d\sqrt{t'} \right] \quad (9)$$

10 with D being the diffusion coefficient, c_0 the initial bulk concentration, t the time and t' a
 11 dummy integration variable. A last aspect that theoretical models are able to predict is the
 12 concentration dependences of the dilational viscoelastic moduli at fixed frequencies. This is
 13 based in the combination of the adsorption models with the definition of the interfacial
 14 dilational viscoelastic moduli as the increase of surface tension against a small change of the
 15 interfacial area A

$$16 \quad \varepsilon^* = \frac{d\gamma}{d \ln A} \quad (10)$$

17

18 **4. Results and discussion**

19 **4.1. Equilibrium surface tension**

1 Figure 1a shows the dependence of the surface pressure on the bulk surfactant concentration
 2 for SLMT solutions and mixtures of PDADMAC and SLMT, as obtained using the drop
 3 profile tensiometer.

4
 5 Figure 1. (a) Surface pressure isotherm for SLMT and PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures
 6 obtained by the drop profile tensiometer. Symbols represent the experimental results and the
 7 lines correspond to the values calculated with the parameters in Table 1. The dotted line
 8 corresponds to PDADMAC – SLMT and the continuous line to SLMT. (b) Total surface
 9 excess for PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures (Γ) calculated using the parameters in Table 1 and
 10 experimental total surface excess (Γ_{NR}) obtained from neutron reflectometry measurements.

11

12 SLMT exhibits an initial steep increase of the surface pressure with increasing bulk surfactant
 13 concentration, as expected for surfactant solutions, until the critical micellar concentration

1 (cmc) is reached at around 10^{-1} mM. When the adsorption of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures
 2 is considered, a synergetic effect was found between the polyelectrolyte and the surfactant on
 3 the surface pressure, i.e. a shift of the surface pressure occurs for surfactant concentrations by
 4 about one order of magnitude to lower bulk surfactant concentrations. The experimental
 5 results of pure SLMT are well described by the Frumkin isotherm.^{50, 52-55} Table 1 summarizes
 6 the parameters obtained from the fit of the experimental results.

7 Table 1. Parameters of the calculated isotherms that described the interfacial adsorption of
 8 SLMT (Frumkin isotherm) and mixtures of PDADMAC – SLMT (Empirical isotherm).

SLMT	PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures
$10^{-5} \omega(\text{m}^2/\text{mol}) = 1.27$	$10^{-5} \omega_{10}(\text{m}^2/\text{mol}) = 2.70$
$a = 1.10$	$10^{-6} \omega_2(\text{m}^2/\text{mol}) = 1.90$
$10^{-1} b (\text{l}/\text{mmol}) = 1.07$	$10^{-2} b (\text{l}/\text{mmol}) = 2.57$
	$\alpha = 0.718$
	$10^3 \varepsilon (\text{m}/\text{mN}) = 6.402$

9

10 For the polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures, the situation is more complex due to their
 11 complex character that requires additional considerations on the development of theoretical
 12 models to provide accurate description of the experimental results. It is possible to find in the
 13 literature theoretical models describing the adsorption of protein – surfactant mixtures.^{52, 56-57}
 14 Despite the binding isotherm has shown that the free surfactant concentration is almost
 15 zero,⁴² which might allow one to approximate the system as a quasi-binary mixture, the
 16 following reasons make the theory non-applicable to the present mixture: a) most proteins are

1 surface active compounds whereas PDADMAC has a negligible surface activity. b) In the
2 system studied, the polymer concentration is above the overlapping concentration, which
3 does not fulfill some of the conditions implicit in the theoretical model.⁵⁸ Furthermore, the
4 interface contains both polymer + surfactant complexes and probably free surfactant (see
5 section on interfacial rheology).

6 Due to the above reasons, we have limited ourselves to the application of an empirical fitting
7 of γ_{eq} , $\gamma(t)$ using a set of equation equation with concentration-independent parameters, yet
8 which also allows us to calculate the total surface excess and the dilational elasticity. We
9 stress that, despite the fact that the equations derive from a theoretical model,⁵⁹ no physical
10 meaning can be ascribed to the values obtained for the parameters given in Table 1.
11 Nevertheless, successful application of the empirical fitting to the experimental data would
12 represent a useful indication of the complexity of the formation of the interfacial layer. Figure
13 1a shows that the calculated curve is able to predict, at least qualitatively, the concentration
14 dependence of the surface tension with the parameters given in Table 1. Figure 1b shows the
15 surface excess curve calculated from the parameters for the PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures at
16 the water / vapor interface. The calculated curve evidences a clear increase of the total
17 surface excess with the bulk concentration in accordance with the dependence found for the
18 total surface excess obtained by neutron reflectometry using structural analysis, as discussed
19 in our previous work (see Figure 1b).⁴²

20 The calculated surface concentration is able to provide a qualitative explanation for the
21 dependence of the total surface excess on the surfactant concentration, although the
22 experimental values are more than twice the theoretical ones. The discrepancies are due to the
23 differences existing between the physico-chemical picture described by the reorientation
24 model and the real situation of adsorbing polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures.

1 4.2. Adsorption kinetics

2 Further insight in the adsorption mechanism of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures at the water /
 3 vapor interface can be obtained from the analysis of the time dependences of the surface
 4 tension obtained using a drop profile tensiometer. Figure 2 shows the time dependence of
 5 surface tension for the adsorption of SLMT (Figure 2a) and PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures
 6 (Figure 3b) at the water / vapor interface for different SLMT concentrations.

7

8 Figure 2. (a) Dynamic surface tension for SLMT solutions with concentrations below the
 9 cmc. The symbols represent the experimental results obtained using a drop profile
 10 tensiometer and the lines correspond to the fitted model using the parameters obtained for the
 11 Frumkin isotherm reported in Table 1. (b) Dynamic surface tension for PDADMAC – SLMT
 12 solutions. The symbols represent the experimental results obtained using a drop profile
 13 tensiometer and the lines correspond to the calculated curves using the parameters reported in
 14 Table 1. Note that in the data corresponding to the PDADMAC – SLMT surface tension
 15 oscillations are shown. These oscillations correspond to sinusoidal surface area perturbations

1 applied to the solution drops during the adsorption process to evaluate the evolution of the
2 dilational elastic modulus during the adsorption process (see below).

3

4 The relatively long time needed for the polyelectrolyte – surfactant layer equilibration, almost
5 three hours, for concentrations close to the cmc of the pure surfactant contrasts with the lower
6 equilibration time needed for the pure surfactant layers, below one hour and with an
7 important dependence on the surfactant concentration. In order to obtain further insights in
8 the adsorption behavior, the experimental data were analyzed introducing the dependences on
9 the surface excesses extracted from the analysis of the surface tension isotherm via the Ward-
10 Tordai equation defined in Eq. (9).⁵¹

11 Figure 2a presents the experimental values of the dynamic surface tension for SLMT solution
12 and the theoretical curves obtained from the Ward-Tordai equation, using a fix value for the
13 diffusion coefficient of about 10^{-10} m²/s for all the surfactant concentrations,⁵²⁻⁵³ and the
14 parameters of the Frumkin model reported in Table 1. The surface tension for the adsorption
15 of SLMT at the water / vapor interface as expected decreases with time. This is the faster the
16 higher the bulk surfactant concentration is. The theoretical and experimental curves present a
17 qualitatively good agreement, especially for times above 10^2 s. However, it is worth
18 mentioning that the qualitative agreement of the experimental data and the theoretical curves
19 allows one to confirm the relatively good description provided by the Frumkin model for the
20 adsorption of SLMT.

21 For the PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures, it was considered that it is possible to use a procedure
22 for the analysis of the experimental results similar to that used for the surfactant solution.
23 However, in this case the adsorption equilibrium has been fitted using Eqs. (3) – (8). Figure
24 2b shows the experimental data obtained using a drop profile tensiometer for the dynamic

1 surface tension of the mixed solutions and the calculated curves obtained using the
2 parameters in Table 1.⁵²⁻⁵³

3 The qualitative trend of the experimental results is similar for both the mixture and the pure
4 surfactant. However, the agreement of the curves obtained by fitting of the experimental
5 results of dynamic surface tension is better for the mixtures. In that case, discrepancies
6 between the experimental results and the calculated ones appear again with the increase of the
7 SLMT concentration. However, for PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures the calculated curves
8 show a faster decrease than the experimental ones. However, similarly to that found for the
9 pure surfactant the theoretical curves provide a good description of the long-time tail of the
10 dynamic surface tension curves.

11 A more accurate description of the adsorption of the mixtures can be carried out in terms of
12 the time dependence of the surfactant surface excess at the water / vapor interface obtained
13 by direct measurements using neutron reflectometry.⁴² Figure 3 represents the time
14 dependence of the surfactant surface excess, Γ_{SLMT} , for the adsorption of polyelectrolyte –
15 surfactant mixtures at different SLMT concentrations (note that the technique is not sensitive
16 to the presence of polyelectrolyte at the interface). Notice that the surface excesses in Figure 3
17 correspond only to the surfactant at the interface, whereas in Figure 1b it was showed the
18 total surface excesses which include the polyelectrolyte and surfactant amounts at the
19 interface.

1

2 Figure 3. Dynamic surfactant surface excesses for the adsorption of PDADMAC – SLMT
 3 solutions with different concentrations at the water / vapor interface as obtained using
 4 neutron reflectometry. Lines are guides for the eyes. Notice that the error bar associated with
 5 each individual point is below the 5% of its value.

6

7 The Γ_{SLMT} dependences on time show the existence of an adsorption of almost 80 % of the
 8 equilibrium surface excess during the first 10^3 s, which may be explained assuming that the
 9 first step of the adsorption process of the mixtures occurs by diffusion from the bulk. From,
 10 the results, it is possible to assume that the reorganization of the material at the interface
 11 allows either further adsorption at the lowest surfactant concentration, or the squeezing out of
 12 material from the interface, leading to a decrease of Γ_{SLMT} for the highest surfactant
 13 concentration. It is worth mentioning that for the lowest SLMT concentrations there is
 14 adsorption of material, as evidenced by the change of Γ_{SLMT} , without any appreciable change
 15 of the surface tension. Thus, it is possible to assume that for the lowest concentration, the

1 surface tension does not provide a real evaluation of the thermodynamic equilibrium of the
2 interfacial layer, as was previously discussed for different systems in literature.^{33, 60-61}

3 **4.3. Dilational rheology**

4 The above discussion concerns features of the adsorption layers and the adsorption kinetics
5 for samples of fixed surface area. However, many technological applications are associated
6 with the response of the system upon mechanical perturbations. Therefore, an understanding
7 of the relaxation mechanisms appearing in the interfacial layers upon a dilational perturbation
8 provide additional useful information on the physico-chemical properties of the system,
9 which is relevant for industrial applications, including foam stabilization or thin film
10 deposition.^{14,62-66} The dependences of the dilational viscoelasticity moduli $\varepsilon^* = \varepsilon' + i \varepsilon''$ (ε' is
11 referred to the dilational elastic modulus and ε'' is the viscous modulus) on the deformation
12 frequency and the interfacial concentration,⁶⁷ will be discussed in this section. In order to
13 complement the above discussion of the adsorption kinetics, the evolution of the elastic
14 modulus during the adsorption processes will be analyzed at a fixed frequency of 50 mHz. It
15 is worth mentioning that the viscous modulus presents a negligible value for all the studied
16 systems, therefore for the sake of simplicity no discussion on its dependences will be here
17 included, note that $\varepsilon' / \varepsilon''$ becomes higher as the surfactant concentration increases. Figure 4
18 shows the dependence of the elastic modulus over time for the adsorption of PDADMAC –
19 SLMT solutions at the water / vapor interface.

1

2 Figure 4. Time dependences for the elastic modulus obtained by the oscillating drop method
 3 at a deformation frequency of 50 mHz for PDADMAC – SLMT solutions with different
 4 surfactant concentrations. The lines are guides for the eyes.

5

6 The time dependence of the elastic modulus agrees well with the results above discussed for
 7 the dynamic surface tension and the dynamic surface excess. The most significant change in
 8 the layer properties occur within the first stage of adsorption (about 10^3 s) for almost all the
 9 concentrations considered. The results show that for the lowest surfactant concentration, a
 10 non-negligible elastic modulus is found which is reasonable considering the non-negligible
 11 adsorption of material obtained from neutron scattering. The elastic modulus increases with
 12 surfactant concentration in the region of higher decrease of the surface tension (see Figure
 13 1a), which is explained by the adsorption of the most part of material at the interface, in this
 14 region the change of the elastic modulus with time is slower. Then, a decrease of the elastic
 15 modulus with concentration until values close to water is observed when the interface is

1 saturated with surfactant. The dynamic elastic modulus provides complementary information
 2 to the above discussion, more specifically about the different processes occurring at different
 3 time scales during the equilibration of the interfacial layers. Figure 5 shows the results, using
 4 a drop profile tensiometer, obtained for solutions of two different concentrations of SLMT
 5 and PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures.

6
 7 Figure 5. Frequency dependences of the elastic moduli for solutions of SLMT (a) and
 8 PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures (b). In both panels, the symbols are referred to different
 9 surfactant concentrations ($\times = 0.03$ mM and $\triangleright = 0.09$ mM) and the lines represent the best fit
 10 of the experimental curves to the corresponding theoretical models described by Eq. (11) for
 11 pure surfactant and Eq. (12) for PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures (see Figure 6).

12

13

14 A detailed analysis of the frequency dependences evidences different behavior for surfactant
 15 solutions and for the polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures. The relaxation of surfactant layers
 16 (Figure 5a) at the water / vapor interface is easily explained assuming the existence of a

1 diffusion controlled process as described by the model proposed by Lucassen – van den
 2 Tempel,⁶⁸⁻⁷⁰ providing the following description of the frequency dependence of the
 3 viscoelasticity modulus

$$4 \quad \varepsilon^* = \frac{1 + \xi + i\xi}{1 + 2\xi + 2\xi^2} \quad (11)$$

5 where $\xi = \sqrt{\frac{\nu_D}{\nu}}$ with ν_D being the characteristic frequency of the diffusion exchange and ν is
 6 the frequency of deformation. Independently of the concentration, the characteristic
 7 frequency of the diffusion, ν_D , assumes values in the range $10^{-2} - 10^{-1}$ Hz.

8 In the case of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures (Figure 6b), the diffusion controlled mechanism
 9 alone does not account for the internal relaxation in the interfacial layers. Similar results were
 10 also obtained for simpler polymer solutions.⁷¹ Thus, the introduction of another relaxation
 11 process to the expression accounting for the viscoelastic modulus is needed. For this purpose,
 12 we follow the description provided by Ravera et al.^{60, 72-73}

$$13 \quad \varepsilon^* = \frac{1 + \xi + i\xi}{1 + 2\xi + 2\xi^2} \left[\varepsilon_0 + (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_0) \frac{1 + i\lambda}{1 + \lambda^2} \right] \quad (12)$$

14 where $\lambda = \nu_1 / \nu$ with ν_1 being the characteristic frequency of the extra relaxation process,
 15 and ε_0 and ε_1 the Gibbs elasticity and the high limit elasticity within the frequency range
 16 considered, respectively. The fact that the aforementioned model provides a description of the
 17 response upon dilation of PDADMAC – SLMT layers may be correlated with the complexity
 18 of the adsorption process discussed above on the basis of the adsorption isotherm. Combining
 19 the adsorption isotherm and the frequency dependences of the elastic modulus, it is possible
 20 to provide an explanation for the equilibration of the adsorption layers of PDADMAC –
 21 SLMT mixtures. First the diffusion-controlled adsorption of the complexes at the subsurface

1 interface takes place, which is followed by a second process of adsorption controlled by the
 2 reorganization of the material adsorbed during the first step. This scenario is similar to that
 3 proposed by Noskov et al.³³ for the adsorption of PDADMAC – SDS at the water / vapor
 4 interface. Figure 6 shows the concentration dependences of the characteristic frequencies
 5 corresponding to the two steps involved in the equilibration of the adsorption layers of the
 6 PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures.

7

8 Figure 6. Concentration dependences for PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures: (a) Frequencies of
 9 the two relaxation processes. (b) Limiting elasticities. The symbols represent the
 10 experimental data and the lines are guides for the eyes. Notice that the error bars are within
 11 the size of the points.

12

13 As expected, the frequency corresponding to the interfacial relaxation process, v_1 , is higher
 14 than that associated with the diffusional transport, v_D . This is easily rationalized considering
 15 that such a process occurs only once the initial adsorption of material at the fluid interface has
 16 taken place. Furthermore, the dependences of the characteristic frequencies on the SLMT

1 concentration are different for ν_D and ν_1 , whereas the former is rather constant or decreases
 2 slightly as the surfactant concentration increases, ν_1 increases with the SLMT concentration.
 3 This can be explained considering that the first step is slightly slowed down with the
 4 surfactant concentration because the increase of the adsorbed amount at the interface
 5 introduces a hindrance, steric or electrostatic, for the adsorption of further material, thus the
 6 first step occurs slowly. The characteristic frequency associated with the diffusion (in the
 7 range $10^{-2} - 10^{-3}$ Hz) is similar to that associated with the diffusion of supramolecular species
 8 found in a previous study.⁶⁰ The detailed analysis of the limiting elasticity values (Figure 6b)
 9 shows clearly that both ε_0 and ε_1 decrease with the surfactant concentration, being as it is
 10 expected $\varepsilon_1 > \varepsilon_0$.

11 Figure 7a shows the concentration dependences of the elastic modulus of SLMT layers. For
 12 sake of simplicity only the results corresponding to some of the frequencies studied are
 13 shown. Other frequencies show similar dependences.

1 Figure 7. (a) Concentration dependences of the elastic modulus for SLMT adsorption layers
2 as were obtained from oscillating drop experiments. (b) Concentration dependences of the
3 elastic modulus for PDADMAC – SLMT adsorption layers as were obtained from oscillating
4 drop experiments. In both panels, the symbols represent the experimental results and the lines
5 represent the values calculated with the parameters in Table 1.

6

7 The results show an increase of the elastic modulus from quasi-null values to reach a
8 maximum which depends on the deformation frequencies, and then further increases of the
9 surfactant concentration leads again to the decrease of the elastic modulus to reach values
10 close to zero. This is the typical behavior expected for the surfactant concentration
11 dependence of the elastic modulus. The theoretical curves calculated using the parameters of
12 the Frumkin isotherm showed in Table 1 agrees qualitatively with the experimental curves,
13 especially as the concentration gets closer to the cmc of the surfactant and at larger
14 frequency.

15 For PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures, the dependence of the elasticity on the surfactant
16 concentration is similar to that found for pure surfactant, as it is shown in Figure 7b. The
17 comparison of the calculated and the experimental data evidences that Eqs. (3) to (8) do not
18 provide a good description of the dilational elastic modulus, which follows given the
19 complexity of the mixture and that the calculated values of Γ are significantly smaller than
20 the experimental ones.

21

22 **5. Conclusions**

23 This work has focused on the adsorption process from mixtures formed by a

1 polyelectrolyte PDADMAC and an oppositely charged surfactant SLMT at the water /
2 vapor interface. The system was studied using a combination of surface tension
3 measurements and neutron reflectometry. The experimental results have evidenced that
4 the adsorption of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures is rather different from that found for the
5 adsorption of pure SLMT solutions. The experimental results indicate that layer formation
6 at the water / vapor interface occurs in a two-step process in which first the adsorption of
7 the bulk formed complexes takes places, and once they are adsorbed an interfacial
8 reorganization of the adsorbed material occurs until the equilibration of the adsorbed
9 layer. This behavior has been described qualitatively in terms of a set of empirical
10 equations, which is compatible with the appearance of two relaxation process in dynamic
11 measurements. Despite the fact that such an equation is able to predict the tensiometric
12 results, it does not provide an accurate quantitative description neither of the surface
13 excesses nor the dilational elastic modulus. Thus, the obtained results underline the
14 complexity of the adsorption processes involved in the adsorption behavior of
15 polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures at fluid interfaces and allow us to conclude that such
16 complex behavior cannot be formally described on the bases of simple thermodynamics
17 models. Therefore, a deeper study on the adsorption of such mixtures must be carried out
18 in order to establish accurately an explanation of the adsorption mechanism, and to
19 develop a theoretical description of this type of mixtures, which is urgently required for
20 the design and optimization of the next generation of polyelectrolyte – surfactant
21 mixtures of technology interest.

22

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7

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1 TOC Graphic

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